

ISic0113

I.Sicily inscription 0113

Language

Latin

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object

bench

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Baths

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. r · a · s · p · i · p

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285160

EDR 110914

EDCS 22100063

Bibliography

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Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese. *Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica.* Palermo / Rome. At 31

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